

A Comparative Study of Serum Pleural Effusion Albumin Gradient (SEAG) and Light's Criteria to Differentiate Exudative and Transudative Pleural Effusion

Mounika Tanna¹, Manas Kumar Mohanty², Raghumanda Sunil Kumar³, Bandaru Madhusudan Patrudu⁴

¹Post Graduate, Department of Pulmonary Medicine, Andhra Medical College, Visakhapatnam

²Associate Professor, Department of Pulmonary Medicine, Andhra Medical College, Visakhapatnam

³Professor & H.O.D., Department of Pulmonary Medicine, Andhra Medical College, Visakhapatnam

⁴Professor, Department of Pulmonary Medicine, Andhra Medical College, Visakhapatnam

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Corresponding Author: Dr. Mounika Tanna

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Abstract:

This study aimed to assess how well Light's Criteria and the Serum Effusion Albumin Gradient (SEAG) distinguished between exudative and transudative pleural effusions. Eighty pleural effusion patients were included in a one-year hospital-based observational study. While SEAG defined 75% of instances as exudates and 25% as transudates, Light's Criteria identified 91.25% of cases as exudates and 8.75% as transudates. While SEAG reported 100% sensitivity for transudates and a better overall accuracy (95%), Light's Criteria showed 100% sensitivity for exudates but misclassified 11% of transudates. The most common cause of transudative effusions was congestive heart failure, whereas the most common cause of exudative effusions was tuberculosis. According to the study, combining Light's Criteria and SEAG increases diagnostic precision and guards against misclassification.

Keywords: Pleural effusion, Light's Criteria, SEAG, Exudates, Transudates.

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Introduction

The pleura, a serous membrane, encapsulates the lung parenchyma, mediastinum, diaphragm, and rib cage, and is divided into the parietal and visceral layers. The lung parenchyma is sheathed by the visceral pleura, while the parietal pleura lines the inside of the thoracic cavity. Between these two layers lies the pleural space, which typically contains a small amount of pleural fluid derived from parietal pleural capillaries and cleared via the pleural lymphatics [1,2]. Pleural effusion, the accumulation of excess fluid in this space, affects about 400 per 100,000 people globally each year, making it one of the most common pulmonary pathologies with diverse etiologies, often manifesting or complicating respiratory or non-respiratory disorders [3,4,5,6].

Pleural effusions are categorized into exudates and transudates based on fluid origin and pathophysiology [7]. Transudative effusions result from systemic changes affecting fluid dynamics, such as heart failure or liver cirrhosis, leading to fluid accumulation. In contrast, exudative effusions arise from alterations in the pleura or capillaries due to conditions like infections, malignancies, or pulmonary embolism, causing localized fluid build-

up. Correctly diagnosing the type of effusion is critical, as treatment strategies differ markedly between transudative, which focuses on managing the underlying condition, and exudative, which requires extensive diagnostic efforts to identify the specific cause [8].

To distinguish between these effusion types, Light's criteria, established in 1972, is the standard diagnostic tool. It deems an effusion exudative if the pleural fluid protein to plasma protein ratio exceeds 0.5, the pleural fluid to serum LDH ratio is above 0.6, or if the pleural fluid LDH exceeds two-thirds the upper normal limit of serum LDH [9]. Although highly effective, Light's criteria misclassify a notable percentage of transudates, prompting the development of other markers like pleural fluid cholesterol and the Serum Effusion Albumin Gradient (SEAG) to improve diagnostic accuracy. This research compares SEAG with Light's Criteria for identifying exudative and transudative pleural effusions. The study compares these two methods to show how a combination strategy could improve diagnostic accuracy, preventing effusion misdiagnosis and improving patient management.

Materials and Methods

The Government Hospital for Chest and Communicable Diseases in Visakhapatnam, Andhra Pradesh, conducted this hospital-based observational cross-sectional study from September 2021 to August 2022. To see if SEAG and Light's Criteria can identify transudative and exudative pleural effusions. The study included 80 pleural effusion patients hospitalised to Pulmonary Medicine. All patients who met inclusion criteria and gave written informed consent were studied.

Inclusion Criteria

1. Patients aged 18 years and above.
2. Both male and female patients.
3. Patients presenting with clinical and radiological evidence of pleural effusion.

Exclusion Criteria

1. Patients diagnosed with empyema or chylothorax.
2. Pregnant or lactating women.
3. Patients unwilling to participate in the study.

All subjects reported age, gender, dyspnoea, chest discomfort, cough, fever, weight loss, and hunger changes. The medical history included heart disease, liver or renal failure, diabetes, and hypertension. Vital signs and a thorough physical were taken.

All study participants had imaging, pleural fluid, and blood testing. We measured serum total protein, albumin, lactate dehydrogenase, CBC, LFT, and RFT. X-rays, ECGs, and chest and abdomen ultrasounds examined pleural effusion severity and extent. Aseptic diagnostic thoracentesis for pleural fluid analysis. The aspirated pleural effusion was analysed for total protein, albumin, LDH, cell count, sugar, Gramme stain, infection culture, AFB for tuberculosis, and malignant cytology. Pleural fluid might be straw-colored, hemorrhagic, or clear.

Two approaches categorised pleural effusions. Light's Criteria defined an effusion as exudative if there was a ratio of pleural fluid protein to serum protein greater than 0.5, a ratio of pleural fluid LDH to serum LDH greater than 0.6, or a ratio greater than two-thirds of the normal upper limit for serum LDH. The Serum Effusion Albumin Gradient (SEAG) was determined using $SEAG = \text{Serum-Pleural Fluid Albumin}$. Serum glutamic acid (SEAG) values above 1.2 g/dL suggest transudative effusions, below indicate exudative. Data was analysed using SPSS (21.0). Continuous blood and pleural fluid protein, albumin, and LDH values were reported as mean $\pm$ SD in the study.

Categories like exudates and transudates were quantified by frequencies and percentages. To diagnose exudative and transudative pleural effusions, Light's Criteria and SEAG's sensitivity, specificity, PPV, and accuracy were calculated. We thoroughly compared the two diagnostic tools to decide which was best.

Results

The study included 80 patients, with an average age of 46.91 ± 17.07 years, diagnosed with pleural effusion. Men (68.8%) outnumbered women (31.3%) in the 18–30 (26%) and 51–60 (26%), patient populations. In adults 41 to 50 years old, exudative pleural effusions were 90.9% common, while in those over 70, transudative were 69% common. The most prevalent clinical symptom was dyspnoea (81.25%), followed by cough (71.25%), fever (56.25%), and chest discomfort (56.25%). Transudates caused dyspnoea (87.5%) and pedal oedema (100%), while exudates caused cough (82.81%). Clinical criteria revealed exudative pleural effusion in 64 individuals (80%) and transudative effusion in 16 (20%). Light's Criteria classified 7 (8.75%) as transudates and 73 (91.25%) as exudates. 60 instances (75%) were exudates and 20 (25%) transudates using the Serum Effusion Albumin Gradient (SEAG). Tuberculosis (38.75%) caused the most exudative pleural effusion, followed by pneumonia (13.75%) and malignancy (25%). Congestive heart failure (56.25%), liver cirrhosis (25%), and chronic renal illness (18.75%) induced transudative effusion.

All transudative effusions were transparent, however 64.06% of exudative effusions were straw-colored. The radiological data showed moderate pleural effusion in 52.5% of patients, large in 33.8%, and mild in 13.8%. Exudates had more moderate and massive effusions (51.56% and 42.18%), while transudates had more mild to moderate effusions. Light's Criteria has 100% exudate sensitivity and 43.75% transudate sensitivity for diagnostic accuracy. The PPV for exudates was 87.67% and for transudates, 100%. Overall, Light's Criteria was 88.75% accurate. In comparison, SEAG had 100% transudate sensitivity and 93.75% exudate sensitivity. It had 100% positive predictive value for exudates and 80% for transudates. SEAG's accuracy was much higher at 95%. SEAG properly recognised all transudates, however Light's Criteria misclassified 11% as exudates. SEAG detects transudates better than Light's Criteria, which detects exudates better, according to the study. Combining the two diagnostic methods prevents pleural effusion type misclassification, improving patient care.

Table 1: Light's criteria

EXUDATES	TRANSUDATES	TOTAL
64 (TP)	0	64
9	7 (TP)	16
73	7	80

Sensitivity for transudates = $7/16 \times 100 = 43.75\%$ Sensitivity for exudates = $64/64 \times 100 = 100\%$
 Positive predictive value (PPV) for transudates = $7/7 \times 100 = 100\%$ Positive predictive value (PPV) for exudates = $64/73 \times 100 = 87.67\%$ Accuracy of Light's criteria = $71/80 \times 100 = 88.75\%$

Table 2: Serum effusion albumin gradient

EXUDATES	TRANSUDATES	TOTAL
60 (TP)	4	64
0	16 (TP)	16
60	20	80

Sensitivity for transudates = $16/16 \times 100 = 100\%$ Sensitivity for exudates = $60/64 \times 100 = 93.75\%$
 Positive predictive value (PPV) for transudates = $16/20 \times 100 = 80\%$ Positive predictive value (PPV) for exudates = $60/60 \times 100 = 100\%$ Accuracy of SEAG = $76/80 \times 100 = 95\%$

Table 3: Sensitivity, PPV, and Accuracy of light's criteria and SEAG

		LIGHT'S CRITERIA	SEAG CRITERIA
SENSITIVITY	EXUDATES	100%	93.75%
	TRANSUDATES	44%	100%
PPV	EXUDATES	88%	100%
	TRANSUDATES	100%	80%
ACCURACY		89%	95%

The sensitivity of exudates according to Light's criteria and SEAG is 100% and 93.75%. The sensitivity of transudates according to Light's criteria and SEAG is 44% and 100%. PPV of exudates according to Light's criteria and SEAG is 88% and 100%.

PPV of transudates according to Light's criteria and SEAG is 100% and 80%. The accuracy of Light's criteria and SEAG is 89% and 95%.

Discussion

This study evaluated Light's Criteria and SEAG for distinguishing exudative versus transudative pleural effusions. Each diagnostic method has pros and

cons, however combining them could improve diagnosis accuracy [10]. Light's Criteria, developed in 1972 and widely used in medicine, works well for defining pleural effusions as transudative or exudative. Standards are based on biochemical indicators, such as serum and pleural fluid protein and LDH levels [11]. Light's Criteria properly categorised most exudates with 100% sensitivity for exudative pleural effusions. The system misclassified 11% of transudates as exudates, which may lead to needless clinical diagnostic testing and treatments. Light's Criteria has similar limits in diuretic-treated and congestive heart failure patients, according to other study.

Transudates may resemble exudates due to fluid balance abnormalities. SEAG's albumin gradient between serum and pleural fluid detects transudates more specifically [12]. SEAG achieved 100% transudate classification accuracy in this study, avoiding Light's Criteria's misclassification issues. In clinical circumstances, transudative effusions from cirrhosis or heart failure must be managed. Pervasive investigations are preferred to careful ones. SEAG had better accuracy (95%) than Light's Criteria but lower exudate sensitivity (93.75%) [13]. This shows SEAG is reliable for transudates and exudates. The study indicated that exudative pleural effusion was predominantly caused by tuberculosis (TB), followed by pneumonia and malignancy. This matches pleural effusion epidemiology in developing countries like India, where tuberculosis is still a major health risk. Transudative effusions are most often caused by congestive heart failure, as internationally. The effusion type must be recognised to aid treatment. Transudative effusions usually resolve with systemic illness treatment, whereas exudative effusions may require more intrusive diagnostics [14,15]. This study suggests that Light's Criteria can diagnose exudates, even though SEAG is better at recognising transudates. Merging the two diagnostic methods reduces misclassification, improving diagnosis and patient outcomes. Further investigations are needed to confirm these findings and determine the optimal therapeutic uses for a combination diagnostic technique.

Conclusion

This study found that Light's Criteria can identify exudative pleural effusions, but it may misclassify many transudative effusions, especially in heart failure patients. SEAG was more accurate at identifying transudates, making it a more reliable categorisation tool. Light's Criteria for exudates and SEAG for transudates increase diagnosis accuracy and reduce misdiagnosis. This may improve clinical decision-making and pleural effusion patient care.

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